

**David Watson
PUBLICATIONS**

CHAPTERS IN BOOKS

Watson, D.M. (1997) "Ratio Analysis of Financial Statements", in *Financial Management in Health Services*, (Ed.) M. Courtney MACLENNAN & PETTY, Brisbane

REFEREED PAPERS AND PRESENTATIONS

Watson, David M. 1996, *Distance Education Materials via the Web – An Australian view*. Paper presented at the World Conference of the Web Society, San Francisco, USA. Proceedings published on CD Rom.

Watson, David M., 1995, "*Emerging Technologies on the Internet*", Paper presented at the International AusWeb 95 conference, Balina, NSW, 2 April 1995

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KEYNOTE ADDRESSES & CONFERENCE PAPERS presented:

Watson, David M. "*Into the 21st Century With Customers and Technology*". Conference address to Customers and Clients of A.C. Nielsen Australasian Conference: 'The Information Challenge - Successful Strategies for a Competitive Edge'. Sydney, September 1993.

Watson, David M. "*Are you making it happen or wondering what happened? Planning for future profit and growth* Keynote address to 150 members of the National Office Machine Dealers Association. Sydney, October 1992

Watson, David M. "*Interventionist Management.*" Keynote Address presented to the 600 members of Australian Nursing Home and Extended Care Association, Adelaide, September 1992.

Watson, David M. "*Surviving the 90's - How the Winners do it!* " Keynote Address presented to 160 members of New South Wales Chemart Pharmacies, Hyatt Coolum, June 1992.

Watson, David M. "*Partnership and Productivity.*" Keynote Address presented to 150 members of Australian Institute of Pharmacy Management, Singapore, May 1992.

Watson, David M. "Management *Styles - Proaction Versus Reaction*" Keynote Address presented to the 300 members of National Association of Nursing Homes and Private Hospitals, Melbourne, April 1992.

Watson, David M. "*Are You a Good Enough Manager?*" Keynote Address presented to the 300 members of National Association of Nursing Homes and Private Hospitals. Sydney, April 1991.

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PUBLIC LECTURES:

Watson, David M. 1995, *Using the Internet for health service education*, Teleconference address to invited guests of the Queensland government and Med-E-Serv Pty. Ltd. on the launch of information technology services. March 29, 1995

OTHER PUBLICATIONS

Barnes, C., Bartnick, R., Brown, A., Cater, P., Cavanagh, T., Hecker, J., Jones, A., Macalpine, D., MacKay, G., McMillan, S., Martin, S., McKenzie, A., Meredith, S., Oates, W., Quinn, G., Robinson, P., Small, M., Smith, G., Vine, K., Williams, A., Watson, D., Watson, K., Worthington, A., Wylie, A., 1994, *The Application of New Technology in UNE's Educational Mission*. Project Group 8 Research Report to the Vice Chancellors Committee on the University of New England's educational mission. UNE Armidale: pp. 49

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- Watson, David M. 1992. Playing the pharmacy management game. *Pharmacy Trade*. May, pp. 10.
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RESEARCH AND COMMUNITY SERVICE

NSW Department of School Education Grant, 1995 \$3000.00
Title: Using Technology tools in Isolated Central Schools

NSW Central Schools staff (Mungindi Project)
 Professional Development In-Service designed to trial creative technological solutions to help meet the needs of isolated teachers. With a colleague, we introduced Web Teaching Resources, email and video conferencing to promote networking and professional support.